

INTRAZONALITY OF GILBERT'S SYNDROME IN A COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF PROVOKING FACTORS IN THE POPULATION.

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Relevance: Gilbert's syndrome (JS) is the most common form of hereditary pigmented hepatitis, which is spread among Europeans 2-5%, Asians 3 %, Africans 36 %. The disease first appears in adolescence and young age, 8-10times more often in males. Provoking factors are prolonged hunger, physical exertion, frequent vomiting. Along with them, the role of neuropsychiatric disorders is given an important place in the development of the disease

Objective: to study the features of the course of CS in the population with a comparative assessment of provoking factors.

Materials and methods of research. To achieve this goal, a group of patients with SF was examined, consisting of 46 people, whose average age was 24.6 ± 4.8 years. Of these, 29 people were represented by the male sex. In each case of LVanamнестически, the specific type of factor that was mainly the sole cause of relapse was carefully identified in the anamnestic history. The diagnosis of SF was established based on the results of clinical, laboratory-biochemical, and echographic studies. In some cases, they used provoking tests, such as fasting, a phenobarbital test, etc.

Results. According to the data obtained, the relapse of SF in the examined individuals occurred mainly against the background of: physical exertion, prolonged hunger, and mental trauma. As follows from the data, in more than half of the cases, a relapse of LV was observed due to physical exertion. Hunger provoked an exacerbation of the disease in 1/3 of the examined persons. Only 5% of patients relapsed as a result of various emotional disorders. It should be noted that physical activity with a large superiority provoked an exacerbation of the disease in persons of the predominantly male sex. The other two factors consistently contributed to the recurrence of CS in the fairer sex. There was also a difference in the rates of recurrent LV. Thus, in individuals with high physical activity, the frequency of relapse of the disease was observed much more often than in starving people and people with mental illness.

Conclusion: based on the conducted studies, it can be concluded that provoking factors have different effects on the frequency of relapse of LV. Among them, the leading one is physical activity, which in more than half of cases contributes to the exacerbation of the disease.

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